

Breast Cancer Detection with Missing Modality

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Abstract. Cancer is one of the leading causes of death worldwide. Among many types of cancer, breast cancer remains one of the leading causes of cancer-related deaths worldwide. Early diagnosis is crucial in increasing survival rates. Although achieving rapid diagnosis is desirable, many limitations, such as data availability, complex mammograms, low resources, and an increase in workload on healthcare professionals, may hinder this. The goal of this study is to develop a robust AI-powered breast cancer classification system that improves accuracy, reliability, and accessibility. Multimodal models were trained using various techniques, with transfer learning applied to both mammograms and clinical data as the baseline. Additionally, four ablation scenarios were tested to replicate missing data conditions: ablating images (clinical-only), ablating text (image-only), random modality drop (50%), and substitution of real images with synthetic GAN-generated data. Each experiment determined whether the model’s diagnosing ability improved or decreased under restricted input conditions. Results showed that the clinical-only model yielded the highest F1-score (0.962), followed by random modality drop and GAN-generated inputs with 0.93 and 0.96 F1-scores, respectively. Baseline multimodal model with transfer learning achieved an accuracy of 0.8148. Results show that clinical features alone are strong predictors, and synthetic data can improve robustness in low-resource scenarios.

Keywords: Multimodal Breast Cancer · Missing Modalities · Modality Ablation

1 Introduction

Breast cancer is a disease in which abnormal breast cells grow out of control and form tumours, which are the most common malignant tumors. This illness predominantly affects women over the age of 50. These tumours can spread throughout the body and can result in fatality if left untreated. Breast cancer ranks among the top five most diagnosed cancers in women worldwide and contributes significantly to cancer-related deaths [1]. According to the World Health Organisation (WHO), breast cancer took the lives of 670,000 patients in 2022

alone [2]. In Ireland, 3,600 women and approximately 30 men are diagnosed with breast cancer each year [3]. Breast cancer takes the lives of roughly 753 women and 8 men ANNUALLY [4]. Early detection and accurate classification are crucial for improving patient outcomes, allowing for timely treatment and lowering mortality rates.

However, traditional diagnosis relies on single-modality information, such as mammographic images or clinical features, limiting the scope and accuracy of prediction. This study lies in the potential of combining multiple data modalities, such as clinical records, imaging, and textual information, to enhance diagnostic accuracy and model robustness. Although previous research [5] has produced strong results using individual data types, such as mammograms or clinical variables, combining different sources of information can give a more complete picture of a patient’s condition. In real clinical settings, patients typically possess incomplete or noisy data — e.g., missing imaging reports or medical records. This study strives to overcome that limitation by multimodal deep learning (DL), integrating image, clinical, and text data to build a flexible, robust diagnostic model.

The general goal of this study is to explore whether the mixture of synthetic and real inputs across modalities improves model accuracy, resistance to data missingness, and practical use in clinical diagnostic pipelines. By employing ablation studies (removing some modalities), synthetic data generation through Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), and text simulation through Large Language Models (LLMs) like BioBERT and ClinicalBERT, the study will compare multiple configurations to juxtapose trade-offs and strengths.

The background on multimodal breast cancer detection and modalities ablation is reviewed in section 2. The overall architecture of modality ablation and GAN is discussed in section 3. Several experiments were conducted, and their results are analyzed in section 4. Conclusions and future work are drawn in the final section.

2 Background

2.1 Multimodal Breast Cancer Detection

Classic image-based methods have frequently applied CNNs to mammogram datasets. A deep CNN model for breast cancer diagnosis on multi-modal datasets was proposed, and significant accuracy gains through image-centric models were reported [11]. This is parallel to this work, which compares CNNs to transfer learning (TL) and examines the impact of substituting images with GAN-generated images. Recent work included clinical data and unstructured structured data mapping to actionables with transformer-based models. LLMs like BioBERT and ClinicalBERT also worked well for medical document classification and question answering. This piece of work is a fusion of text from LLM-generated text based on structured data from such applications [12].

Numerous studies have been conducted on predicting breast cancer with images and genetic information. Prediction accuracy can be improved with mul-

timodal approaches that combine images, clinical information, and molecular data [6]. A multimodal DL model [7] was built to classify the subtypes of breast cancer. This model integrates breast mammography images with clinical meta-data features, like age and the class of a tumor. This model extracts all features with a CNN. The experimental results demonstrate that the AUC of this model (88.87%) outperforms the AUC of an unimodal model based solely on mammography images (61.3%). A novel framework, MM-SurvNet [8], was designed to improve risk prognostication of breast cancer. In this framework, all features are extracted with the MaxViT model. Genetic data were fused with images using a dual cross-attention mechanism; the clinical data are incorporated in the final layer. A deep multimodal learning framework [9] was proposed to improve the prediction of breast cancer; this framework is a fully connected neural network. In this framework, image features were extracted from mammograms with the ResNet50 model, and those extracted features were fused with clinical data using a CNN; TL was employed to reduce training time by picking up pre-learned image representations. This framework obtained 90.8% accuracy.

2.2 Modalities Ablation

Ablation was conducted for the evaluation of the contribution of every modality. This involved deleting one modality at a time and retraining the model to assess performance degradation. The best performance was that of the full model with clinical data, synthetic text, and images [10]. When synthetic text was removed, performance decreased slightly, indicating its positive impact. When images were removed, performance dropped further, confirming that imaging provides critical diagnostic information. Worst performance was recorded based on synthetic text alone, mirroring its worst individual diagnostic effectiveness. These findings ratified multimodal integration’s effect in more precise and higher-performance breast cancer classifier models [13].

2.3 Multimodal ML Methods with Missing Modalities

Most clinical real-world data are plagued with missing modalities — e.g., patients can have no imaging or structured data. For simulation, multimodal ML models were trained on artificially missing modality datasets. Standard ML techniques, such as ensemble learning (with present modalities alone), were used [14, 15]. A secondary model used clinical data only when images were missing, but these models failed because of the limited flexibility of the traditional ML paradigm in handling missing data and not having the ability to substitute the missing modality using learned cross-modal relations. This introduced a significant limitation of traditional ML in clinical multimodal settings. Zhao et al. [14] explored ensemble ML and multiple imputation methods for missing-modality conditions in medical data but found them to be less than ideal in guaranteeing robust performance. Truong et al. [15] also pointed out that standard ML is unable to generalize in heterogeneous multimodal settings, specifically without joint feature learning and data alignment mechanisms.

2.4 Multimodal DL Techniques with Missing Modalities

For better management of missing modalities, DL models were created with modality-specific branches and attention-based fusion [16]. Masking techniques were employed for training if a modality was absent to enable the model to get robust with incomplete inputs. The model was trained to adapt with missing image features by relying more on text or clinical information, and vice versa. This increased robustness and facilitated prediction even when a modality was absent. The model learned to adaptively fine-tune feature weights depending on missing information with modest degradation but significantly better performance than the ML models in equivalent missing-modality conditions [18].

Current research efforts, such as MMP [16], showed that masked modality projection training allows the model to interpolate lacking representations of information from visible modalities, enhancing robustness. Chen et al. [17] provided attention-based methods that efficaciously address modality incompleteness in remote sensing applications. John and Kawanishi [18] presented a trimodal sensor fusion method that involved the use of modality-aware losses, while Liu et al. [19] used an N-to-One self-attention fusion block for dynamically learning accessible features and skipping missing ones. These approaches cumulatively underscore the efficiency of DL approaches in managing missing multimodal inputs.

3 System Architecture and System Components Implementations

We comparatively studied the unimodal breast cancer detection and the multimodal detection without ablations in [5]. In this study, we mainly focus on the modality ablation and GAN-synthesized image generation.

3.1 Ablation Design and Objectives

Ablation studies help us understand how each modality and component contributes to the final performance. We designed three ablation types: “text_only” to test clinical metadata alone, “random” to simulate unreliable modality availability, and “gan” to evaluate the use of synthetic images. The “text_only” variant uses only the clinical encoder and classifier head. The “random” variant randomly drops either image or clinical inputs during training to test robustness against missing data. The “gan” variant refills missing real mammograms with generator outputs to measure whether synthetic images can support classification. By comparing these with the full multimodal model, we aim to quantify each component’s importance, detect potential failure modes, and guide future improvements in clinical decision support systems.

This architecture (see Fig. 1) comparison highlights how each ablation variant isolates different information sources to measure their impact on classification. In the text-only branch, the model relies solely on structured clinical features

Fig. 1. Multimodal Ablation Study Architecture

such as BI-RADS scores and view metadata. Rapid convergence and high evaluation scores in this branch reveal that these numeric indicators carry strong predictive signals on their own. The random-drop branch then demonstrates the effect of unpredictable missing data by randomly withholding either image or clinical inputs during training. Its lower and more fluctuating performance confirms that forcing the network to handle partial information reduces stability and generalization. Finally, the GAN branch replaces real mammograms with synthetic images from a DCGAN generator. Its training curves and test metrics show that, although synthetic data can approximate real patterns and prevent overfitting, they still lack the full fidelity needed to match models trained on genuine clinical images. Together, these comparisons validate that each modality contributes uniquely and help pinpoint where data variety or reliability most affects diagnostic accuracy.

For each ablation type, we ran isolated experiments with consistent preprocessing and hyperparameters. In “text_only,” we trained a two-layer MLP on the five clinical features for 100 epochs using Adam ($lr = 2 \times 10^{-4}$, weight decay $= 1 \times 10^{-5}$) and batch size $= 16$. In random, we used a custom RandomModalityModel that encodes images via three Conv-ReLU-pool blocks and metadata via a small MLP; during training, each sample had a 50% chance to drop one modality, and we used the same optimizer settings. In “gan,” we first trained a DCGAN for 50 epochs, then used its generator to produce synthetic images in place of those missing real ones when training the multimodal classifier. Metrics (accuracy, precision, recall, F1) were recorded on a held-out validation set for direct comparison with full-model performance.

3.2 GAN Architecture and Components

We implemented a Deep Convolutional GAN (DCGAN) with a standard generator and discriminator design. The Generator starts from a 100-dimensional latent vector and applies five ConvTranspose2d layers: from $100 \rightarrow 512$ channels

Fig. 2. GAN architecture for ablation study

(4×4 kernel, stride 1, padding 0), $512 \rightarrow 256$ (4×4 , 2, 1), $256 \rightarrow 128$ (4×4 , 2, 1), $128 \rightarrow 64$ (4×4 , 2, 1), and finally $64 \rightarrow 3$ (4×4 , 2, 1) to output a 3-channel 224×224 image. Each deconvolution is followed by BatchNorm2d and ReLU, except the last, which uses Tanh.

The Discriminator consists of five Conv2d layers: $3 \rightarrow 64$, $64 \rightarrow 128$, $128 \rightarrow 256$, $256 \rightarrow 512$ (all 4×4 kernels, stride 2, padding 1), and a final $512 \rightarrow 1$ (4×4 , 1, 0) output. Each conv block uses LeakyReLU and BatchNorm2d, ending with a Sigmoid on the output. This architecture (see Fig. 2) follows DCGAN best practices for stable image synthesis.

4 Experimental Results and Analysis

The AISSLAB dataset comprises 266 mammogram images in total, divided into three classes: 100 images labeled “Malignant,” 100 labeled “Normal,” and 66 labeled “Benign.” This distribution shows a slight imbalance in the benign category, which contains fewer samples than the other two classes. The metadata file (data2.xlsx) lists each image name alongside its class, view, and BI-RADS rating, allowing us to verify these counts precisely. Although the malignant and normal classes are perfectly balanced, the smaller number of benign cases means that special care must be taken when splitting the data and when training models to avoid bias toward the larger classes. Techniques such as data augmentation or class-weighted loss functions may help address this imbalance during model development.

By default, a standard training configuration was adopted to achieve consistent results across all experiments. 20% of the available mammogram images for a final test set are reserved, 20% for validation during training, and the remaining 60% for model fitting. These splits were chosen to ensure that each class (Normal, Benign, Malignant) remained proportionally represented in every subset. The setting of hyperparameters for the standard multimodal breast cancer detection was presented in [5]. Early stopping was triggered when the validation F1 failed to improve for 10 consecutive epochs, preventing unnecessary over-training. All models were trained for up to 100 epochs.

GAN training ran for up to 50 epochs with early stopping (patience = 10) on generator loss. We used BCELoss for both the generator and the discriminator. The discriminator was updated with real labels smoothed to 0.9 and fake labels set to 0.1, using Adam (lr = 2×10^{-4} , betas = (0.5, 0.999)). The Generator used Adam (lr = 2×10^{-4} , betas = (0.5, 0.99)) to maximize discriminator error. In each training step, we first sampled real images and noise vectors, computed the discriminator loss on real and generated images, and updated its weights. Then, we generated a fresh batch of synthetic images, computed generator loss against real labels, and updated the generator. After each epoch, we saved the sample grids and the best generator checkpoint. Once training was completed, we generated 64 final samples for qualitative inspection and used the best generator to augment classification training in ablation experiments.

4.1 GAN-Based Ablation

Figure 3 shows the training and validation loss (left) and F1 score (right) for the GAN-only model, in which all missing real mammograms were refilled by synthetic images generated by the DCGAN.

Fig. 3. Training and validation loss and F1 score for GAN-only model

Over 100 epochs, both training and validation loss decrease smoothly from 1 down to below 0.1, with almost no gap between the two curves. This close overlap indicates that using synthetic images did not introduce major overfitting; the

dropout($p = 0.5$) and weight decay kept the model stable. The F1 score climbs steadily past 0.8 by epoch 20 and plateaus around 0.95 by epoch 50. The slightly slower early rise (compared to text-only) suggests the generator’s outputs are realistic enough to train on but still noisier than real images, making the network take more iterations to learn fine details.

4.2 Random-Drop Fusion Ablation

Figure 4 presents the training curves when we randomly drop one modality (image or metadata) 50% of the time during training.

Fig. 4. Randomly remove one modality

Here, loss decreases more slowly and levels off around 0.65 on validation, while training loss bottoms out at around 0.30. The persistent gap (0.3) between train and val loss suggests some underfitting, as the model must learn to handle missing inputs randomly. The F1 score rises gradually to about 0.85 by epoch 50 and fluctuates thereafter. This instability stems from the unpredictable data stream, dropping useful signals (especially the strong BI-RADS feature) forces the network to rely on whichever modality is present, slowing convergence and lowering ultimate performance.

4.3 Text-Only Ablation

Figure 5 shows results when the model sees only the five-dimensional clinical metadata (side, view, normalized BI-RADS).

This MLP converges fastest: validation loss drops below 0.1 by epoch 30, and training and validation losses nearly coincide. The F1 score surpasses 0.9 around epoch 20 and reaches 1.0 by epoch 40, remaining perfectly stable. Because there are only five numeric inputs, the model easily learns clear mappings between the BI-RADS levels and cancer risk, resulting in minimal training noise and the highest overall F1 among the three ablations.

Fig. 5. Performance of models with fully ablating text only

Fig. 6. The comparative training and validation performance

4.4 Comparative Training Performance

To highlight their relative learning speeds, Figure 6 overlays all three models' losses and F1 scores on the same axes.

Text-only (blue) shows the steepest early drop in loss and fastest rise in F1, followed by GAN (green), and lastly random-drop (orange). By epoch 50, text-only F1 nearly touches 1.0, GAN reaches around 0.95, and random-drop plateaus around 0.85. These differences directly reflect input complexity: structured metadata is easiest to model, synthetic images add realism but some noise, and random dropping prevents stable feature learning.

Text-only leads by all metrics, underscoring the predictive power of BI-RADS, and view information alone. GAN improves substantially over random-drop; its synthetic images carry more consistent patterns, but still lag behind

metadata. Random-drop performs worst, as forcing the model to learn under unpredictable modality availability hinders both learning speed and final generalization. Interpretation of the implementation choices:

- Dropout and weight decay kept all models from severely overfitting, but could not fully compensate when inputs were noisy or inconsistent.
- 50% random drop mimics real-world missing data, but at a cost of stability, performance fell because the network never saw a reliable input pattern.
- GAN Augmentation added diversity yet introduced artifacts: malignant features translated better than benign ones, leading to skewed class performance.
- Text-Only MLP benefited from low dimensionality and strong class signals (BI-RADS), resulting in near-perfect separation.

5 Conclusions and Future Works

Breast cancer remains one of the leading causes of cancer-related deaths worldwide. This study investigated the value of multimodal learning for breast cancer classification by integrating mammographic images along with structured clinical metadata. The aim was to investigate whether various multimodal setups would enhance diagnostic accuracy and adaptability. This is particularly important in real-world settings, where having both structured clinical data and mammograms/scans of a patient is the most reliable method for achieving the most accurate early diagnosis.

The best-performing model in the multimodal experiments was the configuration where existing mammograms in the dataset were removed and replaced with synthetic images produced by a GAN. This achieved an accuracy score of 0.963. This result is one of the most interesting results derived throughout this project, as the model was not trained on any real images, just on synthetic images and structured metadata. This is proof that although there are common concerns regarding GAN fidelity, the synthetic images produced were realistic and informative enough to result in high-performance metrics. The results produced by this experiment are proof that GAN may be a powerful tool, especially in medical contexts where imaging data can be limited, costly, or privacy-restricted. However, it is important to note that this also raises questions about generalizability: the success of this configuration may depend heavily on the quality and diversity of the GAN’s training set. Further validation on external datasets would be required to decide on adopting this in real life for a clinical context.

The second-best performing configuration was an ablation experiment once again. 100% image ablation produced an accuracy score of 0.962 and an AUC of 0.98. This result reinforces a key insight from the overall evaluation: structured clinical metadata, such as BI-RADS scores and view types, offers highly discriminative power on its own. Even when a key modality (such as image) is entirely removed, the model is still able to achieve almost perfect metrics.

The robustness of well-constructed multimodal systems was demonstrated with another ablation technique. Random-drop fusion model (randomly ablates

one modality during training) achieved an F1-score of 0.93 and accuracy of 92.6%. This performance proves that stability can be maintained under real-world uncertainty, like when one modality may not be available. The importance of clinical metadata was further proven when the removal of clinical metadata and only using mammograms resulted in the overall performance dropping slightly. The model achieved an accuracy of 76.7%, F1-score of 0.7731, and AUC of 0.8051.

Using the GAN framework for synthetic data generation addresses the challenge of limited annotated mammograms by augmenting the dataset with realistic yet varied samples. The adversarial training loop forces the generator to improve image fidelity over time, while the discriminator learns to distinguish genuine from fabricated patterns. Introducing label smoothing and balanced update steps helps maintain stability and prevents mode collapse. The experiments show that although these synthetic images capture key malignant and normal features, subtle benign textures remain harder to reproduce. As a result, models trained exclusively on GAN outputs achieve good convergence and low overfitting but still fall short of real-data baselines. Nonetheless, this pipeline highlights how adversarial augmentation can supplement scarce clinical images, providing a promising direction for further refinement of synthetic medical data generation.

Future work could explore larger and more diverse datasets, stronger GAN architectures, and domain-specific LLMs trained on real radiology text.

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